
Knowledge Management Approaches in Pakistani Universities: Faculty Perceptions

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Abstract

Knowledge management is defined as the process of developing, validating, presenting, sharing, and implementing knowledge. Knowledge management (KM) is a strategy for aiding organisations in identifying, choosing, organising, and disseminating the knowledge and skills necessary for tasks including strategic planning, dynamic learning, problem solving, and decision making. Educational institutions played a significant role in the development, management, and dissemination of information and knowledge among higher education institutions. The study's objectives were to learn about (1) faculty perspectives of existing knowledge management approaches, (2) the advantages of knowledge management practises, and (3) the current hurdles to adopting knowledge management practises effectively in Pakistani universities. Participants in the study were all PhD supervisors who had been approved by all public and private institutions in Pakistan. During the interview process, researcher spoke with a total of 15 PhD supervisors. As a basis for qualitative data analysis, grounded theory was employed. Research revealed that Pakistani institutions have a poor understanding of knowledge management. However, despite the fact that universities in Pakistan were well aware of the benefits of knowledge management methods, they did not make any attempts to adopt them. Knowledge management approaches in Pakistan are afflicted by difficulties related to perspectives and ICTs due to a dearth of frameworks, coordination points, and budgetary concerns in the country's institutions. The findings indicated that knowledge management approaches are required in Pakistani universities. It was concluded in this research that knowledge management practices have not been completely included into the planned agendas of most institutions Knowledge management strategies, plans, and policy guidelines are recommended by the study for universities to create.

Keywords: Knowledge, management, approaches, strategic planning, perceptions.

INTRODUCTION:

Knowledge management is a term that has been used by different researchers in different contexts. By some academics, it is characterised as knowledge management since it involves the creation of information, its distribution, and its subsequent re-application. There was a wide range of viewpoints on the issue of knowledge management. Knowledge management techniques are primarily concerned with connecting individual and organisational knowledge in an appropriate manner. To be successful in knowledge management, you need the correct knowledge in the right place at the right time. When it comes to developing countries, knowledge management techniques are still nascent.

University administrators and students may find knowledge management beneficial. It was noted by Seonghee and Boryung (2008) that the use of knowledge management is helpful to

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five key areas of learning in universities: curriculum creation; academic researches; administration methods; and cooperation and enhancement of students' results. As Laal (2011) points out, those that are unable to adapt to the changes in Knowledge Management will not survive. It has been suggested that higher education institutions can benefit from knowledge management methods such as formal training of employees, information repositories, knowledge fairs, and chat rooms by Shams, Rad and Hoochmand (2009). For example, Aggarwal Kiran, & Verma (2011) argue that universities are the centres of knowledge in higher education. Aquisition and distribution of information is considered as two of the most essential features of Knowledge Management in higher education institutions. A university is the location where information is created and disseminated, generally via research and creation. According to Yaghi and Zamzami (2014), knowledge management at Saudi Arabia's higher education institutions is essential and must be implemented. It is possible that knowledge management might help to the enhancement of university performance in the complicated situation of institutions. Knowledge management has an influence on organisational decision-making, administrative issues, research and development, and curriculum creation (Kidwell et al.,2000). In their work, Waheed, Arshad, and Kashif (2011) argue that businesses require a knowledge management environment in order to get better outcomes. 'Knowledge management' concepts and practices can help Pakistani university students, says Mikulecky (2009). Learning to organise and preserve papers internally as well as using knowledge management to disseminate inter-discipline information will help. It was discovered in a research by Shah and Mahmood (2015) that knowledge management is a relatively young topic in Pakistan, both within and outside of academia and the workplace. It was determined that the knowledge management strategies used by Pakistani institutions were conceptually and practically flawed through the study of journals published internationally and nationally as well as proceedings from conferences.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

Students in universities and colleges in the 21st century confront a wide range of difficulties and barriers in their academic pursuits. Advanced technology is critical to the development and growth of a knowledge-based economy in the 21st century. In today's Globalized world, more and more organisations rely on brainpower to achieve competitive advantages. Everything from manufacturing to information management has evolved throughout the years. A country's ability to compete depends on its ability to manage its knowledge. Knowledge management was born as a result of this as knowledge assets. The problem of this research was to look at how Pakistani institutions handled practices of knowledge management.

STUDY GOALS:

This study's goals were as follows:

1. To find out how PhDs supervisors at Pakistani universities feel about knowledge management approaches.
2. To determine the value of knowledge management techniques in Pakistani universities.
3. To investigate the present challenges that Pakistani institutions face in effectively using Knowledge Management approaches.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

1. What do Pakistani PhD supervisors believe about knowledge management?
2. What are the benefits of utilising knowledge management at universities in Pakistan?
3. What obstacles do Pakistani universities face in implementing Knowledge Management practices?

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY:

- The current study of knowledge management strategies in Pakistani universities has the potential to benefit Pakistan's higher education institutions.
- In terms of promoting and utilising knowledge management benefits, the study's practical significance was shown in the development of virtuous identification of knowledge management at Pakistani institutions.
- The findings of the study might be useful in identifying key management practices, problems, and barriers, as well as assisting in the implementation of knowledge management at Pakistani institutions.

STUDY METHODOLOGY:

The objective of the study was to undertake a qualitative examination of knowledge management approaches in Pakistani institutions.

THE STUDY'S POPULATION AND SAMPLING:

Out of 4636 PhD supervisors, the researcher chose 465. For the qualitative portion of the research, theoretical sampling was employed. Theoretical sampling was used to choose PhD-approved supervisors for qualitative interviews in order to get a broad picture of knowledge management practices at Pakistani universities. The duration of the interviews ranged from 30 to 45 minutes.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT:

To comprehend the phenomenon of knowledge management practices, the study goal required the opinions of PhD certified supervisors. Interviews were utilised as a data collecting tool to study the in-depth perceptions of PhDs in Pakistani institutions. An open-ended interview technique for qualitative interviews was utilised to gather information about knowledge management approaches employed in Pakistani universities.

DATA COLLECTION:

Data gathering is the most important and challenging component of research investigations. Data was also gathered through personal visits and Skype interviews with the study's respondents.

DATA ANALYSIS:

The qualitative data derived from the interview methods was organised into themes in line with the study goals, and narrative testimony was utilised in conjunction with a quantitative presentation based on grounded theory.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:

Ethical and morally good research is the goal. Ethics in research is becoming more and more essential. Respondents pose ethical dilemmas for researchers according to Sekaran and Bougie (2016). Researchers must maintain respondents' information confidential. Participants' replies would be kept as anonymous as feasible, with no mention of the participants' identities in the study.

THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF DATA:

Assessing qualitative research data with thematic analysis is one of the most significant methods of analysing qualitative data. As stated by Kvale and Brinkmann (2009), it is the process of examining, using qualitative data to capture, and then discover key patterns (themes) direct relevance to the topic under investigation.

TRANSCRIBING THE INTERVIEWS:

In total, 15 interviews were recorded and transcribed. The transcript contains all of the questions and responses from the interviews, which are all indexed. Ground theory was used to identify the key themes based on the aims and testimonies. Fundamentally, grounded theory is the methodical development of theories that are grounded on particular evidence. It was also useful for developing new theoretical groups from the data using grounded theory's tools.

PERCEPTION OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT APPROACHES:

Interviewees in Pakistani universities had a limited awareness of knowledge management practices, as evidenced by their answers. During interviews, respondents used terminology such as information communication technology, information system, and research activities repeatedly. There was no mention of tacit or explicit terms in any of the interviews. Some people were completely ignorant of the existence of knowledge management process systems. There was a majority of supervisors who did not know what knowledge management was at their various universities. One respondent confused knowledge management practices with quality enhancement cells in Pakistani universities. When asked about knowledge management techniques and processes, one respondent had no idea what the term meant. According to respondents from public institutions, "knowledge management techniques at Pakistani universities are not taken seriously." Respondents to interviews expressed their belief that research reports and publications are the primary means of documenting and storing knowledge at Pakistani institutions. The two responders from private sector institutions demonstrated a clear understanding of knowledge management and its applications activities because universities provided knowledge management students with a course. Knowledge management plans, units, and officers were absent in Pakistani institutions, which explains why it hasn't become popular yet. At another interview, it was said that "knowledge management in Pakistani institutions is essential for the country's prosperity."

THE BENEFITS OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT PRACTISES:

PhDs approved supervisors interviewed at Pakistan's governmental and private institutions

of education are aware of the advantages of knowledge management approaches. Those who took part in the interviews were quite clear about how knowledge management techniques may enhance management learning, improve efficiency of institutions, reduce operational costs of projects, improve organisational learning process, and improve quality of service. Those interviewed at public institutions were aware of the need of promoting knowledge exchange across the many stakeholders. Participants in a research study claimed "knowledge management methods can increase the productivity of university employees and PhD teachers in Pakistan." It is time for higher education commission to adopt knowledge management in universities of Pakistan, says a respondent from private institutions: "Knowledge management practices required great training to investigate the benefits of knowledge management." Respondents from higher education There was a lack of knowledge management at Pakistani universities compared to other world-class schools. Knowing how to effectively handle knowledge was deemed the most crucial practice by PhDs supervisors in Pakistani universities.

CHALLENGES IN KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN PAKISTANI UNIVERSITIES:

From the respondents' interviews, it became clear that there were a number of major obstacles to the successful application and implementation of knowledge management approaches in Pakistani institutions. The respondents were quite clear about the fact that universities faced more problems than they did rewards. They also verified that Pakistani institutions rely heavily on seminars and multimedia to share information with one another. Knowledge management approaches in Pakistani universities are not taken seriously, according to the respondents, and nobody cares about protecting knowledge assets in their specific university. Universities in Pakistan are capable of grasping a great deal of knowledge, but this knowledge is not properly used to the university's advancement." Another responder from Pakistan's private institutions believes that knowledge management is not engaged in the university's dynamic distinguishing function. Another responder from one of Pakistan's new public sector institutions stated that "knowledge management approaches in Pakistani universities demand high level technologies, and there is a great need for technology infrastructure to implement such practices." Knowledge generation in universities is perceived as a one-way process by the respondents. Overall, interviewees feel a sense of responsibility for maintaining their own knowledge, according to most respondents. Answers to such question were echoed by the respondents. As well as the absence of IT infrastructure and organisational structure at Pakistan's universities as well as the lack of senior assistance and an inability to integrate advanced technology.

FINDINGS:

- Many of the respondents were actively involved in controlling their own information, which they viewed in some respects as knowledge management techniques.
- Major obstacles to implementing knowledge management techniques in Pakistan include a lack of information technology infrastructures, organisational structure, strategy, and a lack of leadership support.
- According to responses, PhD supervisors from public and private universities were aware of the potential benefits of knowledge management approaches at the university

level. Some of the most essential features included enhanced management learning and increased efficiency of institutions via the use of information technology.

- Knowledge management in Pakistani universities can only be effective if the staff is properly trained.
- Universities in both the public and private sectors have there is just a limited amount of high-level technology integration.
- There is an urgent need for knowledge management initiatives in Pakistani institutions, based on the findings of the qualitative research.
- It was shown that supervisors who have been allowed to supervise PhD students knew about the major benefits of knowledge management approaches.
- An important reason why knowledge management initiatives in Pakistan have not been implemented is the lack of support from authorities.
- There is a lack of regard for knowledge management approaches at Pakistani institutions, and no one cares or is concerned about the preservation of intellectual assets in their particular university.

DISCUSSION:

The vast majority of respondents were ignorant of Supported by Parikh (2001) and Gooijer (2000), and Joshi, Holsapple (2002). Knowledge management maturity level in the Pakistani universities were discovered by accident. Respondents to a research on business intelligence, knowledge-based E-learning, believed that supporting technologies were necessary to accomplish knowledge management. It was especially difficult to capture tacit knowledge at Pakistani institutions, as Tsoukas (2005) points out in his piece Do we really comprehend tacit knowledge. Plentiful research was conducted (Davenport and Völpel, 2001) Wong (2005), Liebowitz (1999) Skryme, Amidon (1997) and Skryme (1997) agree with the study, database and its software, ICT, portals, are the most required components for knowledge management adoption in businesses. According to the study's findings, the majority of respondents said that knowledge management practices are urgently needed in Pakistani higher education, which is confirmed by research by Yusoff, Mahmood, Jaafar and Salak (2012), Abbas, Hayat, Shahzad, & Riaz, (2011), Yaghi and Zamzami (2014). According to the research's respondents, knowledge management advantages in higher education may be realised via effective implementation, which is confirmed by the study of Liebowitz (1999).

CONCLUSIONS:

Research study's conclusions were based on its results and discussion.

- The notion of knowledge management at Pakistani universities was unknown to supervisors.
- Pakistani universities have no official knowledge management plan or coordinating center; KM practices were rare.
- Lack of finance, lack of leadership support, and the advantages of knowledge management methods were recognised as obstacles to overcome.
- As a result of a deficiency in IT infrastructure and a lack of knowledge management strategy, universities in Pakistan struggled to effectively implement knowledge management.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Pakistani universities can prepare for knowledge management through their strategic plan and integrate it in their long-term strategic goals.
- All public and private sector higher education institutions can establish and integrate knowledge management techniques in their vision and mission statements, as well.
- Universities may have access to some of the most advanced technology available for knowledge management techniques.

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